

INVESTIGATION OF THE SATUS OF THE SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMS UNDER SANSAD ADARSH GRAM YOJANA IN RAJGOLI VILLAGE IN KOLHAPUR DISTRICT

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Abstract

The paper is about the social development programs implemented under the Sansad Adarsh Gram Yojana (SAGY) in Rajgoli Village in Kolhapur district. It is objected to analyze the effectiveness of programs expected to implement for the social development of the villagers in the Rajgoli village, i.e., selected in the first phase of SAGY in Kolhapur district. Initially, the researcher did a baseline survey for situation analysis. Accordingly, an impact analysis was made after the intervention by the Government authorities. The paper assesses the effectiveness and impact of voluntary efforts and the programs implemented by government machinery. The paper also highlights the importance of people's participation in the successful execution of government schemes and programs.

Key Words- social development, SAGY, Social Work Intervention, Communal Harmony, Nutrition, Gender.

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Introduction:

The term "social development" refers to constructing independence and self-confidence and working independently and collaboratively to change interpersonal interactions, organizations, and discourses that exclude and maintain poor people. The level of investment of individuals (such as land, housing, livestock, savings) and their competence (such as good health and education), socio-economic (such as social connectedness, identity, leadership relations), and psychological (such as the ability to hold other people accountable) significantly affects poor people's ability to hold others responsible and to empower themselves (self-esteem, self-confidence, the ability to imagine and dream of a better future). Folk's collective assets and skills, such as voice, organization, representation, and identification, are also crucial.

According to Midgley, "social development is the human interactions and the complex phenomena that arise from the specific interactions like a large number of groups and associations including the family, neighbourhood associations, formal organizations, communities, and even societies which also give rise to social networks, values, cultures, and institutions" (Midgley, (2014).)

Participation in local groups and effective intercommunity improvement by people living in poverty can help them achieve social empowerment by enhancing their skills, knowledge, and self-perception. Local associations, such as farming cooperatives or microfinance groups, also serve as self-help structures through which poor people coordinate their economic activity.

Social Development in SAGY

In a dynamic and multifaceted development process, social development involves planned social change that aims to promote and secure the well-being of the entire population. Although it is cascaded at the functional level, the definition encompasses numerous elements of the design phase beyond the economic one.

Methodology :

The study aims to understand the applicability of SAGY with special reference to health care. In the past 75 years of rural development in India, few attempts have been made to understand the ground realities of the nation. In today's changing world, where people's perceptions and social institutions' structures are rapidly evolving, the rural healthcare system needs to have a different dimensional view and become updated with its changing surrounding to address the contemporary problems of the agrarian society. The data was obtained from villagers of Rajgoli Khurd village. Primary data were elicited using a structured interview schedule, non-participatory observations and fieldwork to meet the objectives set out for the research and test the hypothesis mentioned above. The secondary data was gathered from various books, government records, magazines, journals etc.

The guidelines of SAGY (2014) suggest that every MP select one village and attempt to 2016 make it a model village. In 2014 three MPs selected the following three villages in Kolhapur District: Rajgoli Khurd village is the most populous village among these villages, so the researcher chose Rajgoli Khurd village as a sample for the present study. Taro Yamane Formula of sampling was selected to determine the total sample selection of the village. (<https://www.academia.edu/>, n.d.) To choose the sample from the Vadi -Vasti, proportionate stratified random sampling was used. But the respondents were selected by purposive sampling, so a multi-stage sampling method was adopted for the research. The field data were collected

twice before and after the implementation of SAGY in January 2015 and December 2021. The same samples were tested before and after the implementation of SAGY. A Case study of selected villages has been conducted separately.

Table No 1: Vadi-Vasti-wise number of Households and chosen samples

Sr. No.	Name of the village	Name of Vadi /Vasti	No. of households	No of the selected samples by proportionate stratified random sampling
1	Rajgoli Khurd	Chenatti	110	41
2		Rajewadi	18	7
3		Ganeshwadi	40	15
4		Rajgoli	491	186
Total			659	249

(Source: Field Data)

A Weighted Mean of Variables

The weighted Mean is calculated before and after implementation. A weighted mean is an average. Instead of each data point contributing equally to the final mean, some data points contribute more "weight" than others. If all the weights are equal, then the weighted mean equals the arithmetic mean (the regular "average" you're used to). Weighted means are very common in statistics, especially when studying populations.

In simple terms, the formula can be written as:

$$\text{Weighted mean} = \frac{\sum wx}{\sum w}$$

- Σ = summation (in other words...add them up!).
- w = the weights.
- x = the value. (htt4)

The study area of this study was the Kolhapur district of Maharashtra state, and the empirical research was carried out in Rajgoli Village. The study is limited to one village only.

In the present study, the researcher has through light on social development activities implemented under SAGY with the following parameters:

Indicators of the Social Development

Table No 2 Indicators of the Social Development

Objective	Program
communal harmony	Communal harmony
	Dissolution of Interpersonal conflict at the village level
Social development programs	Participation of people in S.H.G.s
	Performance of S.H.G.s
	Participation Youth with zeal

Status of clean home and community	Participation of Youth Mandal
	Work of Bharat Nirman volunteers
	Organization of sports competition
	A collective celebration of National festivals
	Use of toilets
	Construction of soak pit
	Clean gutters
	Segregated garbage deposits to G.P.
	Cleanliness Public urinals
	Cleanliness and beautification of roads.
Cleanliness and beautification of public places.	

(Source: SAGY Guidelines, annexe-I, Page No.21)

Intervention for Social Development

Table No. 3: Intervention for Social Development

Name of the Scheme	Name of Program	status
Self-Founds	Vibrant and harmonious community society.	Village level awareness M.S.W. students conducted programs
	Voluntarism like Bharat Nirman Volunteers.	Bharat Nirman Volunteers appointed
	The capacity building of the people to fully participate and contribute to local development.	Village level awareness M.S.W. students conducted programs
	Felicitation of women, successful people.	On Independence day
	Violence and crime-free community.	Tantamuki Abhiyan
	Establishment of citizen committees.	The work has not been done
	Sensitization of especially youths.	Village level awareness M.S.W. students conducted programs
	The organization of sports and folk art festivals.	-

(Source: Field data and Progress Report 06/12/2021 Village panchayat Rajgoli (Khurd))

Creating a vibrant and harmonious village society is essential for the government's smooth functioning. Promoting activities like Bharat Nirman Volunteers will build the capacity of the people to participate fully and contribute to local development. Activities for honouring village elders and local role models, especially women, freedom fighters, and martyrs, will create rational human beings. They were being and doing generate the capability. Sensitization, especially of youth, and village sports and folk arts festivals will reduce the violence and crime

in the village. The formation of Citizen Committees will serve the purpose. Village songs can be created with the help of the local poets to integrate the villagers to instil a sense of pride among the people; the 'Village Day' can be implemented through the M.S.W. student volunteers of the Y.C.S.R.D. Celebration of the village day through exhibitions and honouring the village elders would be the local role models, especially women, freedom fighters and martyrs. Village discussions on local production, productivity, and employment would create a sense of belonging among the villagers. The schemes like Bharat Nirman Volunteers, Youth Club schemes, M.P.L.A.D.S. and I.E.C. components of the appropriate scheme would be useful for generating the social force for village development.

A United and harmonious village and a crime-free society would be the outcome of this model. The female population is higher due to the male migration towards urban employment in the village.

Table No 4: The Intervention Programs for Clean Village

Name of the Scheme	Name of Program	Status of Work
	Identify all houses without Individual Household Latrines (I.H.H.L.) and facilitate the construction of toilets in each household.	A total of 166 Toilets were constructed
S.B.M.	Identification of lack of toilets in all public institutions and facilities for construction.	3 Units of 2 toilets were constructed
	Promote the use of toilets – both individual and institutional.	Conducted awareness rallies
S.L.W.M.	Garbage collection, segregation and disposal systems.	An advanced system of wastewater and solid waste is established
Self-funds	Behaviour change campaigns on hygiene and sanitation through the involvement of youth groups and social communication methods like street theatre and puppetry for an open defecation-free community.	Conducted awareness rallies, street plays and other awareness programs were conducted.

(Source: Field data and Progress Report 06/12/2021 Village panchayat Rajgoli (Khurd))

There are several types of pollution in villages that threaten health the most. Providing universal access to sanitation, including household toilets for all, public toilets and their maintenance, solid and liquid waste management, and biogas plants attached to toilets is critical to enhancing village health. A village's progress can be guaranteed if proper planning is implemented. It was necessary to identify households without Individual Household Toilets

(I.H.H.L.) and facilitate the construction of toilets in each household with government assistance. When designing the scheme, it was difficult to identify funding sources and find gaps in public institutions. One hundred sixty-six individuals and three units of public toilets were constructed in the village by students of M.S.W. An awareness campaign was conducted. Using techniques such as street drama, group discussion, and personal understanding, volunteer steers and government organizations worked honestly and accurately. Several government-sponsored schemes were used to construct covered drains, liquid waste treatment pits, and waste collection, segregation, and disposal systems. I.E.C. took the initiative to demand and promote the use of toilets in individual and institutional systems. A defecation-free village and clean village roads and public places encourage villagers to adopt a better lifestyle.

Evaluation and participation of the people in Social development programs

Table No. 5 Pre-intervention and post-intervention weighted mean of assessed variables to understand scenarios of social development

Sr. No	Programs	Pre-intervention weighted mean	Post-intervention weighted mean	The difference between pre-and post-intervention weighted mean
1.	Communal harmony	124.5	124.5	0
2.	Dissolution of Interpersonal conflict at the village level	85.53	108.33	23
3.	Participation of people in SHGs	56.33	112.5	56.17
4.	Performance of SHGs	111.5	113.83	2.33
5.	Participation Youth with zeal	41.5	124.5	83
6.	Participation of Youth Mandal	41.5	124.5	83
7.	Work of Bharat Nirman volunteers	41.5	124.5	83
8.	Organization of sports competition	41.5	124.5	83
9.	A collective celebration of National festivals	124.5	124.5	0
10.	Use of toilets	74.5	124.5	50
11.	Construction of soak pit	83	124.5	41.5
12.	Clean gutters	41.5	124.5	83

13.	Segregated garbage deposits to GP	91.83	124.5	32.67
14.	Cleanliness Public urinals	41.5	124.5	83
15.	Cleanliness and beautification of roads.	41.5	124.5	83
16.	The cleanliness and beautification of public places.	41.5	124.5	83

(Source: Field Survey)

1. For any village or nation to achieve communal harmony, it is important to maintain their physical, social, and environmental well-being. Harmony is inherent, while humans create discord. The impact of conflicts between communities or social disagreements on the economy and social development is profound. Incentives and investments alone cannot promote long-term economic development. For economic and social development to occur, several factors must be in place, including the establishment of the rule of law and the legal system, the development of organizations and their capabilities, the advancement of learning, the development of a value system essential for economic growth, and many others. It was found that 249 respondents (100%) favour promoting communal harmony in the village before and after the intervention.
2. The village did not appear to be experiencing communal conflict. Thus, the villagers believed their lives were inhomogeneous before implementing the program. Since the villages already had a pleasant environment, no special efforts were required under SAGY. As a result, the weighted mean is raised from 85.33 to 108.33. It has been stated that there has been a growth of 23. There is no doubt that the conflict redressal committee is working efficiently due to this report. As a result of the changing attitudes toward conflict resolution, people have adopted a new approach.
3. According to the survey results following the intervention program, 71.08% of respondents reported that they actively participated in SHGS, and 28.92% reported participating to some degree in SHGS. Consequently, the weighted mean has increased from 56.33 to 112.5. This represents a growth of 56.17 percentage points. Several new SHGs have been formed, and villager engagement and efficiency have increased. It has also been observed that the approach to SHGS has changed among the villagers. Upon completion of the intervention program, 74.3% of the respondents agreed that SHGS performed well, and 25.7% indicated it had some effectiveness. Therefore, the weighted

mean has been raised from 111.5 to 113.83. As indicated, there has been an increase of 2.33. It illustrates the establishment of new SHGs and increased activity and efficiency among villagers. There has also been a change in the approach to SHGS among the villagers. SHGs have been recognized for their importance, and their performance has been praised.

4. Almost all of the respondents agreed that they were unaware of the participation of youth in social programs before the program's implementation. Following the intervention program, 100% of respondents agreed that youth should be actively involved in social programs. Thus, the weighted mean has been raised from 41.5 to 124.5, which indicates a significant growth of 83. Youth are actively involved in community development programs, as evidenced by this project. It has been observed that the approach of the youth to development has changed over time. It was reported that 100% of respondents were unaware that the youth club was involved in social programs before the program's implementation. According to the respondents, 100% agreed that the youth club actively participated in social programs after the intervention program. Consequently, the weighted mean has increased from 41.5 to 124.5. A significant increase of 83 has been observed. Youth clubs are actively involved in developing community programs, as shown in the picture. Quite a few changes have been made to the youth club's approach to development.
5. In the survey, 100% of respondents stated that they were unaware of the Bharat Nirman volunteers' involvement in social programs before executing them. As a result of the intervention program, 249 (100%) of the respondents indicated that Bharat Nirman volunteers had satisfactorily participated in the social programs administered by the organization. This results in an increase in the weighted mean (from 41.5) to (124.5). According to the data, there has been an increase of 83 points. It demonstrates the active involvement of Bharat Nirman volunteers in community development programs. There has been a significant change in how the Bharat Nirman volunteers approach development. According to the respondents, no sports competitions were organized at the village level before awareness programs. Upon completion of the intervention program, 100% of the respondents reported that village-level sports competitions had been organized. This way, the weighted mean is raised (from 41.5) to (124.5). A significant increase of 83 points has been observed. In intervention programs, there was

an effort to create a feeling of homogeneity among youth; sports were organized at the village level. It also observed that 'we feeling' among villagers after the program. There has been a change in the way people approach development.

6. 100% of respondents agreed that villages should celebrate national festivals communally. As a result of this program's implementation, it has been demonstrated that villagers were peaceful and believed in a uniform way of life before it was implemented. It is important to point out that they participated in the national programs as a village community despite their disparities on several fronts. As long as the peaceful culture already existed in the villages under SAGY, there was no need to create any more efforts to maintain it.
7. All 249 (100%) respondents said they regularly used the toilets after the intervention program. Due to this, the weighted mean has increased (from 74.5 to 124.5). This represents a growth of 50 points. Before the program, the majority of villagers used open defecation. Following the completion of the program, toilets were constructed and regularly used. There has been a change in how people approach their hygiene and the hygiene of their communities. The intervention program resulted in the unanimous agreement of all 249 respondents (100%) that soak pits should be constructed in the village. This results in a higher weighted mean (from 83 to 124.5). An increase of (41.5) has been observed. A part of the village authority's wastewater management program was the construction of soak pits in the village, which was done with the help of volunteers as a part of the program's execution. All respondents (100%) admitted that garbage was not segregated and deposited in the village panchayat after the intervention program. Consequently, the weighted mean has been raised (from 41.5) to (124.5). In other words, there has been a substantial increase of 83 points.
8. This image shows that as part of the local government's waste management program, segregated garbage is collected by the local government. Following the intervention program, all respondents (100%) agreed that the gutters in the village were regularly cleaned. This results in an increase in the weighted mean (from 91.83) to (124.5). This represents a 32.67 per cent increase. There has been an improvement in the efficiency of the village council as a result of this. People's perception of a clean environment has changed over time due to technological advancements. All respondents (100%) agreed that public urinals were not cleaned regularly before awareness programs were

implemented. It was found that all 249 (100%) of the respondents agreed that public urinals are cleaned regularly due to the intervention program. As a result, the weighted mean is raised (from 41.5) to (124.5). It has been seen that there has been a significant growth of (83).

9. There has been an improvement in the efficiency of the village authority. Among people, the approach to maintaining a clean environment has changed a lot over the last few decades. A comparison of respondents' views regarding the cleanliness and beautification of roads before and after the program is presented in Table 6.4.21. All (100%) of the respondents agreed that there was no cleanliness and no beautification of roads before awareness programs were conducted. It was found that 100% of respondents agreed that roads should be cleaned and beautified regularly after the intervention program. As a result, the weighted mean is raised (from 41.5) to (124.5). It has been seen that there has been a significant growth of (83). The village authority has achieved a high-efficiency level due to this project. People's perception of a clean environment has changed over time due to technological advancements. All (100%) respondents agreed that public places lacked cleanliness and beautification before awareness programs. It was found that all (100%) of the respondents agreed that roads should be regularly cleaned and beautified following the intervention program. The village authority has achieved a high-efficiency level due to this project. People's perception of a clean environment has changed over time due to technological advancements.

Hypothesis testing: -

The researcher determined the Null and Alternative hypotheses regarding human development among health and educational infrastructure and the workforce's efficiency.

1. **Null Hypothesis (H₀)** - There is no significant difference between pre-intervention and post-intervention in the participation of the villagers and infrastructural development in the village.
2. **Alternative Hypothesis (H₁)** - There is a significant difference between pre-intervention and post-intervention in the villagers' participation and infrastructural development in the village.

TableNo 6: Results of t-Test: Paired Two Samples for Means

t-Test: Paired Two Samples for Means		
	Pre Intervention	Post Intervention
Mean	67.73063	122.0725
Variance	1011.48	28.33558
Observations	16	16
Pearson Correlation	-0.24337	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	15	
t Stat	-6.48867	
P(T<=t) one-tail	5.11E-06	
t Critical one-tail	1.75305	
P(T<=t) two-tail	1.02E-05	
t Critical two-tail	2.13145	

In Table 6, the researcher found the significance /p-value is less than 0.05, indicating a significant difference.

Hence, the researcher accepts H_0 is rejected, and the intervention has significantly changed social development conditions. Therefore, the villagers have improved their participation in social development programs and are aware of the importance of keeping a clean home, public places, and community environment.

Conclusion :

The prerequisites of an integrated approach to Rural Development especially to enhance the Social Development scenario. People's participation and awareness about their rights. The study indicates the Parliamentary representation of the people can bring about the changes at grassroots if it is efficient enough.

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